

Monitoring the genetic diversity of *Salmonella* spp in three breeder-fattener farms over time

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BACKGROUND

Salmonella was the second most commonly reported food-borne gastrointestinal infection in humans in the European Union in 2023. In pig farms, asymptomatic carriage is common. In 2023, the French exploratory study showed that 56% of pig farms were positive for *Salmonella*. The most common serotypes were the monophasic variant of *S. Typhimurium* (1,4,[5],12:i:-) (40,8%) and *S. Derby* (29,8%) [1]. The aim of this project was to monitor three pig farms with clinical Salmonellosis and to determine the diversity of the strains they may carry over time

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Herds A, B and C were monitored over a 6-, 10- and 17-months period respectively. The three herds were breeder-fattener farms but in herd A, the pigs were born on one site and fattened on two different sites. Herds A, B and C were visited 5, 7 and 11 times respectively between 2022 and 2024. Sampling was performed from feces on the pens of fattening rooms (10 feces pieces for a total of 50 g). The detection of *Salmonella* was carried out according to the NF U 47-100 standard. Serotyping of *Salmonella* isolates was performed according to the White-Kauffmann-Le Minor scheme [3]. Genomic DNA profiles of the isolated strains were determined using *Xba*I according to the pulsotyping standardized protocol developed by the CDC in Atlanta USA (PulseNet) [2].

RESULTS

In all three herds, 97% of the 101 strains isolated belonged to serotypes *S. Typhimurium* 1,4,[5],12:i:- (TMV) and *S. Derby*, *S. Typhimurium* 1,4,[5],12:i:- being largely prevalent (88%). The remaining strains belonged to serotypes *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Agona* and *S. Mbandaka*. In herds B and C, pulsotyping showed that up to 6 different strains of *S. Typhimurium* 1,4,[5],12:i:- were identified over time. In herd C, types SC-23-SImC-01 and SC-24-SImC-06 were regularly identified showing that they probably colonized them (Figure 1). In herd A, strains identified were different according to the fattening site, types SC-23-SImA-02 and SC-24-SImA-01 being specific to fattening sites 1 and 2 respectively, showing that the environment plays a role in the *Salmonella* contamination of the herd (Figure 2).

DISCUSSION and CONCLUSION

Our results showed that pig herds can be contaminated with several strains of different serotypes confirming existing results. Indeed, several routes of contamination coexist within the same farm such as feed, water, air, pests, equipment or humans [4]. However, this contradicts results we obtained in a previous study exploring the genetic diversity of *Salmonella* strains isolated from one pig herd with clinical salmonellosis. Indeed, we showed that two unique strains of *S. Typhimurium* and *S. Rissen* colonized the herd over a five-years period [5].

Figure 1: Genomic diversity of *Salmonella* isolates within herd C

Figure 2. Genomic diversity of *Salmonella* isolates within herd A

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